

IEA Wind Task 52 - 18 m/s Hurdles report - Low Hanging Winds Team

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CAPE posgraduate course - 2024 edition - Montevideo - Uruguay - Prof. Dr. David Schlipf

Abstract—This work presents the results of a study aimed at optimizing Lidar-based wind measurements for wind turbine control applications. The focus is on processing Continuous Wave (CW) Lidar data to improve the accuracy of Rotor Effective Wind Speed (REWS) estimation and reduce associated errors. Various methodologies were explored, including brute-force optimization of Lidar parameters, linear regression techniques, and advanced machine learning models such as Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, random forest, gradient boosting, and feedforward neural networks. Results show that optimizing Lidar settings, particularly using a 30-degree CW Lidar, significantly reduced measurement error by 44%. However, further attempts with straightforward and segmented linear regressions did not improve performance over that threshold. Advanced machine learning methods showed a slight improvement, achieving a minimum cost function value of 0.1897 m/s. Analysis revealed that the Lidar’s estimation delay, especially during sudden wind speed changes, contributes to the remaining errors. The present work concludes that further optimization of machine learning models and Lidar processing techniques could yield improved accuracy in Lidar-based wind speed estimation.

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1. Methodology and Results

1.1. Optimized base case

The LiDAR FeedForward scripts included in the WindTask repository considered the use of a 4 Beam pulsed Lidar and a Circular Continuous Wave (CW) 15 degree LiDAR. The lower costs with such instruments were in the 0.35 m/s area, particularly 0.3525 m/s for a 15 degree CW LiDAR with a cutoff frequency of 0.3268 Rad/s and a buffer time of 6.1111s.

The first change performed to the given scripts was to adapt them for the use of a 30 degree CW LiDAR. That implied modifying the OpenFAST input files. Once performed such changes and ran the OpenFAST simulations, the buffer time and cutoff frequency were adjusted via Brute Force optimization (see Fig. 1)

Figure 1. Brut-Force optimization results for buffer time and cutoff frequency with 30 deg CW LiDAR

Such optimization converged to a buffer time of 2.58 and a cutoff frequency of 0.44 Rad/s that meant a cost of 0.1984 m/s, making this the reference value of cost for further optimization attempts.

1.2. Straightforward linear regression attempts

Once identified the base case, the first attempts on reducing the error were performing linear regressions considering the main variables involved in the wind field determination. Through all the regressions considered in this section, the first three seeds were used for training, and the last three to evaluate the performance. For those seeds, the reference cost is 0.19 m/s. In this section, V_{lidar} represents the mean of the LiDAR measurements of the previous second.

1.2.1. REWS vs Lidar estimate

In this section, the Rotor Effective Wind Speed (REWS) estimation was performed as a linear regression of the Lidar (V_{lidar}) estimate used in the base case as introduced in equation 1

$$REWS = a.V_{lidar} + b \tag{1}$$

from Eq. 1 a would be the slope and b the intercept. This methodology resulted in a cost of 0.229 m/s of the error in comparison with the overall error of the base case.

1.2.2. Segmented linear regression

Here the REWS estimation depended on the V_{lidar} magnitude. Three different linear regressions were performed depending on the V_{lidar} value, being the thresholds between the areas 16 m/s and 19 m/s for the three zones case (see eq. 3)

$$\begin{aligned} \text{if } V_{lidar} < 16 \text{ m/s} : REWS &= a_1.V_{lidar} + b_1 \\ \text{if } 16 \text{ m/s} < V_{lidar} < 19 \text{ m/s} : REWS &= a_2.V_{lidar} + b_2 \\ \text{if } V_{lidar} > 19 \text{ m/s} : REWS &= a_3.V_{lidar} + b_3 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

and 16 m/s, 19 m/s and 20 m/s for the 4 zones case.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{if } V_{lidar} < 16 \text{ m/s} : REWS = a_1 \cdot V_{lidar} + b_1 \\
& \text{if } 16 \text{ m/s} < V_{lidar} < 19 \text{ m/s} : REWS = a_2 \cdot V_{lidar} + b_2 \\
& \text{if } 19 \text{ m/s} < V_{lidar} < 20 \text{ m/s} : REWS = a_3 \cdot V_{lidar} + b_3 \\
& \text{if } V_{lidar} > 19 \text{ m/s} : REWS = a_4 \cdot V_{lidar} + b_4
\end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

They both resulted in an increase on the error in comparison with the base case (see Tab. 1)

Table 1. Segmented linear regression effect on error

3 areas	4 areas
0.191 m/s	0.193 m/s

Cost results for segmented linear regressions

1.2.3. Multi-variable linear regression: V_{lidar} and mean $\frac{\delta V_{lidar}}{\delta t}$ in $t-0.5s < t < t$

Here, the effect of a multi-variable linear regression was studied. In this case, V_{lidar} and the mean value for the previous half second of the time derivative estimate were used as the input variables. The resulting cost function for the last three seeds is of 0.222 m/s

1.2.4. Straightforward linear regression: Summary

Table 2 presents a summary of the effect of all the methodologies introduced in the section on the error.

Table 2. Straightforward linear regression results summary

Method	Effect on mean error
V_{lidar} LR	0.229 m/s
3 areas LR	0.191 m/s
4 areas LR	0.193 m/s
Multi-Variable LR	0.222 m/s

LR: Linear Regression

1.3. Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) Neural Networks attempts

Here, LSTM neural networks were used to predict the REWS from the available data. In order to do so, the first 4 seeds were used to train, and the last 2 to verify. In those last 2, the average cost was 0.186 m/s.

1.3.1. Input data set 1

Continuing with more advanced regression models, LSTM neural networks were implemented. The input data employed was:

Input data

- Lidar measurement time series, buffered 5.2 seconds. (40 measures per second)
- Blade pitch angle
- Rotor speed
- Tower base pitching moment.

Here, the first would be the instantaneous measurements of the Lidar, buffered 5.2 seconds to consider the difference in the timestamps of the REWS from Turbsim and the Lidar measurement signal. The others were considered after an initial analysis on the correlation between all the outputs and the REWS from Turbsim, being those the ones that showed the best values.

Target data

- REWS from Turbsim

The model can be adjusted with a series of hyperparameters such as number neurons, loss function and window size. For this attempt, we trained the model with the following hyperparameters:

- Number of neurons: 2 - 8 - 30 - 120
- Loss function: MAE - MSE
- Windows Size: The last 160 measurements.

The results are shown in table 3

Table 3. Test results for the current model

H-Parameters	BIAS [m/s]	MAE [m/s] (cost)	MSE [m/s]	Cor [%]
1N - MAE	0.010	0.418	0.277	93.23
1N - MSE	0.018	0.410	0.267	93.47
2N - MAE	-0.006	0.313	0.156	96.23
2N - MSE	-0.034	0.343	0.187	95.49
8N - MAE	-0.018	0.332	0.180	95.67
8N - MSE	-0.005	0.334	0.180	95.65

As can be seen, the results with this post-processing technique lead to larger cost values than the base case. LSTM neural networks are very useful for this kind of data analysis, and have the potential to provide better results, but as the input data did not include the Lidar-REWS, it does not. The initial decision to not include them and use the instantaneous measurements of the Lidar was based on the need to provide a better description of the wind speed estimate first derivative, something explained in detail in section 1.7. It is also interesting to observe that as the amount of neurons increase, the cost function also does. That can be explained by an overfitting of the model to the training data.

1.3.2. Input data set 2

Here, the methodology implemented was analogous to the one of the previous subsection, but using the following input data set and hyperparameters:

Input data

- Lidar REWS

Target data

- Number of neurons: 1 - 2 - 8
- Loss function: MAE - MSE
- Windows Size: The last 160 measurements.

Table 4. Test results for the current model

H-Parameters	BIAS [m/s]	MAE [m/s] (cost)	MSE [m/s]	Cor [%]
1N - MAE	0.013	0.188	0.055	98.78
1N - MSE	-0.013	0.190	0.055	98.76
2N - MAE	-0.006	0.191	0.056	98.73
2N - MSE	-0.011	0.191	0.056	98.75
8N - MAE	0.0	0.191	0.057	98.72
8N - MSE	-0.013	0.191	0.056	98.74

1.4. Random Forest Machine Learning Algorithm

Here we used the first 3 seeds to train and seeds 4 to 6 to test. For this last 3 seeds, the cost function is 0.19 m/s. For this methodology, we used the Matlab function "TreeBagger.m" with the following input data and hyperparameters

Input data

- Lidar REWS
- Instantaneous Lidar measurement
- Pitch angle
- Tower base pitching moment
- Lidar REWS time derivative mean for the previous half second
- Lidar REWS time derivative mean between $t-1.5s$ and $t-1s$

111 **Target data**

112 • REWS from Turbsim

113 **Hyper Parameters**

114 • Number of trees: 50

115 • Leaf size: 2

116 Using this methodology in the post-processing resulted in a cost

117 function of **0.1898 m/s**

118 1.5. Gradient Boosting

119 Here we used the first 3 seeds to train and seeds 4 to 6 to test. For this

120 last 3 seeds the cost function is 0.19 m/s For this methodology we

121 used the Matlab function "fitrensemble.m" with the following input

122 data and hyperparameters

123 Input data

- 124 • Lidar REWS
- 125 • Instantaneous Lidar measurement
- 126 • Pitch angle
- 127 • Tower base pitching moment
- 128 • Lidar REWS time derivative mean for the previous half second
- 129 • Lidar REWS time derivative mean between t-1.5s and t-1s

130 Target data

- 131 • REWS from Turbsim

132 Hyper Parameters

- 133 • Number of learning cycles: 200
- 134 • Leaf size: 2
- 135 • Default for the rest of the parameters

136 Using this methodology in the post-processing resulted in a cost func-

137 tion of **0.1897 m/s**

138 1.6. Feed Forward Neural Network

139 Here we used the first 3 seeds to train and seeds 4 to 6 to test. For this

140 last 3 seeds the cost function is 0.19 m/s For this Artificial Neural Net-

141 work methodology we used the Matlab function "feedforwardnet.m"

142 with the following input data and hyperparameters

143 Input data

- 144 • Lidar REWS
- 145 • Instantaneous Lidar measurement
- 146 • Pitch angle
- 147 • Tower base pitching moment
- 148 • Lidar REWS time derivative mean for the previous half second
- 149 • Lidar REWS time derivative mean between t-1.5s and t-1s

150 Target data

- 151 • REWS from Turbsim

152 Hyper Parameters

- 153 • Hidden Layers: 20

154 Using this methodology in the post-processing resulted in a cost

155 function of **0.1898 m/s**

156 1.7. Analysis on the sources of error

157 An initial qualitative analysis resulted in identifying that the Lidar

158 estimation provided to the wind turbine feed forward control accuracy

159 was low when local maxima and minima of the REWS were observed

160 (see fig 2)

161 Analyzing the Lidar data processing script CalculateREWSfrom-

162 LidarData_LDP_v1.m it became clear that the methodology used

163 for the estimation of the Lidar wind speed used a mean of the Lidar

164 registered values during the last second, including a full ring of 40

pointwise measurements. Such methodology seems to produce a

wind speed estimation with certain "inertia" that lacks of capacity to

respond to sudden changes. That is also observed when analyzing

the relationship between the mean error at the time step "t" and the

REWS time derivative at $t - 1s$ (see fig.3)

Figure 3 plots the mean error of the population whose time deriva-

tive of the REWS at time step $t - 1s$ on bins of such time derivative.

The time derivative is calculated from the REWS computed from

the Turbsim, being the real "observed" data. This result allows us to

conclude that big increases on the approaching wind speed result on

a delayed underestimation of the observed wind speed by the Lidar,

while important decreases on the approaching wind speed result on a

delayed overestimation of the observed wind speed by the Lidar, con-

sistent with the incapacity to respond to such changes qualitatively

observed in Fig.2.

180 2. Conclusions

In comparison with the LiDAR data provided, using a 30-degree

angle continuous wave LiDAR probes to perform better, resulting in a

reduction of 44 % of the cost function after a Brute-force optimization

of the buffer time and cutoff frequency. The initial attempts on using

linear regressions to provide a reduction of the cost function were

unfruitful. Even tough, it can be concluded that segmented linear

regressions showed lower costs than multi-variable and simple linear-

Regressions.

LSTM neural networks were implemented in section 2.3 with two

input datasets. As well as the linear regressions, the attempt didn't

show a reduction on the cost function. Moreover, there are many

combinations regarding input datasets and window size that wasn't

explored in the present work.

Sections 2.4 to 2.6 present the data on three attempts on using firstly

machine learning and later artificial neural network techniques to

reduce the cost function. There, six input data series were used

according to an initial correlation analysis between them and the

REWS estimated from Turbsim. They all resulted in a small reduction

of the cost function for the last three seed. The authors consider that

further work in this line may lead to even better results, as there is

still work to do regarding the hyperparameters' selection.

In section 2.7 a relationship between the mean value of the errors

and the time derivative of the REWS from Turbsim at t-1s is analyzed.

It is shown how lower values of the time derivative relate to larger

magnitude negative values of the mean error, while larger positive

values of the time derivative relate to larger positive values of the

mean error. That is interpreted as a delay in the response to changes

of the estimation of the REWS from LiDAR data, the product of an

inertia in its estimation coming from the way such value is estimated

from the measurements (using the last second results). Those results

could not be reproduced with LiDAR data. As a clear relationship is

observed between the Turbsim derivative estimation and the error, a

good LiDAR estimation of the time derivative would allow a linear

regression adjustment, concluding that a measuring methodology

that allows a better estimation of such time derivative would lead to

a reduction in the cost function.

(a) Lidar estimation and observed REWS for seed 6

(b) Lidar estimation and observed REWS for seed 6: Zoom on peaks

Figure 2. REWS and Lidar estimation

Figure 3. Bar plot of mean error vs REWS time derivative at $t - 1s$. Seed 6